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Determinants Of Neonatal Umbilical Cord Care Practice Among Mothers In Rivers West Senatorial District, Rivers State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the determinants of neonatal umbilical cord care practice among mothers in Rivers West Senatorial District, Rivers State. A descriptive correlational survey design was adopted for the study with a population which consisted of three hundred and fifty-four thousand, five hundred and fifty-six (354,556) postpartum women in Rivers West Senatorial District. The sample size for the study was 880 which were selected using the multi-stage sampling procedure. The study instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire title: Neonatal Umbilical Cord Care Questionnaire (NUCCQ), with a reliability coefficient of 0.76. Data was analyzed with the aid of the Statistical Product for Service Solution (SPSS) version 23.0 using point biserial correlation at 0.05 level of significance. The finding of the study revealed that there was a statistically significant relationship between practice of neonatal umbilical cord care and other factors such as place of delivery ($n = 811$; $r = 0.82$; $p < 0.05$), location of delivery ($n = 811$; $r = 0.61$; $p < 0.05$), and attitude towards cord care ($n = 811$; $r = 0.79$; $p < 0.05$). It was concluded that neonatal umbilical cord is determined by several factors as enumerated above. It was recommended among others that Government should make delivery in Primary healthcare facilities free of charge to encourage women deliver in healthcare facilities where they can be monitored and assisted in the proper care of the neonatal umbilical cord.

Keywords: Care, Determinants, Mothers, Neonate, Umbilical Cord

INTRODUCTION

Any effort geared towards reducing neonatal morbidity and mortality must not ignore proper cord care practices, which is helpful in alleviating neonatal deaths. According to the World Health Organization (WHO, 2017), neonatal deaths accounted for 46% of the 2.6 million under-five deaths, which translated into the death of 7000 newborns every day; of which 32% of such deaths was primary caused by infections (Ministry of Health, 2018). Sacks et al. (2015) revealed that, in Zambia, many deliveries were done outside of health facilities, and this gives way for the use of many different applications on the umbilical cord. Mothers were known to apply substances like petroleum jelly, cooking oil, baby lotion and breast milk on the umbilical cord. There are some who apply powders of roots, burnt gourds and ashes. In Ghana, Asiedu et al. (2019) reported that, majority (85.7%) of the mothers used substances that have not been recommended for cord dressing such as shea butter and hot water while 64.3% used unapproved dressings such as herbs, salt, ground banana peels mixed with shea butter, sand mixed with salt, chalk mixed with salt and strong antiseptics such as Dettol. In Nigeria, studies revealed that umbilical cord infections results in 30% – 49% of deaths in neonates. Nigeria therefore ranks the second

highest globally, with 276 000 deaths annually resulting from umbilical cord infection (Lawn et al., 2015; Okpaleke, 2017).

Although cord cleansing after delivery is viewed as mainstay of neonatal care, the substances and method of application are not consistent with the best practice guidelines (Osuchukwu et al., 2017). That notwithstanding, Padiyath, et al. (2015) showed that, despite the efforts to improve cord care practices in many rural areas where deliveries are conducted by untrained hands, guidelines for umbilical cord care are seldom followed due largely to ignorance. Moreso, Sacks et al. (2015), noted that, care of the neonate's umbilical cord is crucial during the neonatal stage of life and poor umbilical cord practices have been linked with infections.

New born care is of immense importance for the proper development and healthy life of a baby. Over the years, there has been an improvement on cord care Practices which might have resulted from increased awareness regarding safe delivery practices, high percentage of institutional delivery and presence of skilled birth attendants. (Abhulimhen-iyoha, & Ibadin, 2015). The place of residence and knowledge of cord care are also determinants of cord care practices. Health facility delivery, place of residence, and knowledge of cord care were the determinants of cord care. The reason for this might be related to the idea that delivery in a health facility is likely to afford them other good advice on the care of her child (cord care inclusive).

The recommended practice in the treatment of umbilical stump is hygiene with soap and water and antiseptics with 70% alcohol (Ibrahim et al., 2015; Linhares et al., 2015). World Health Organization (2016) advocates dry cord care in those countries with adequate obstetric care and low neonatal mortality rate. In recent years, new studies and reviews attribute some benefit to applying chlorhexidine on the umbilical stump. Similarly, Nosan and Para-Panjan (2017) noted that, the basic principle of umbilical cord care is to keep it clean and dry, as this provides the fastest and safest umbilical cord healing.

Specific suggestions for managing a freshly cut umbilical cord stump include hand washing, application of chlorhexidine gel and keeping the cord stump covered minimally with the baby's usual clothing in low-resource countries (Walsh et al., 2017). To practice the foregoing might be challenging if there is no adequate knowledge about it. Dhingra et al. (2015) reported that education of mothers on chlorhexidine at the community level showed appreciable knowledge and increased acceptance of chlorhexidine amongst mothers. Muriuki et al. (2017) noted that, the high neonatal mortality rate may indicate a lack of knowledge. Aside knowledge, several other factors were found to determine umbilical cord care practice among mothers. According to Abhulimhen-Iyoha and Ibadin (2015), the determinants of good cord practices include literacy level of them other, place of delivery, cultural beliefs, influence of an elderly role figure, advice from other women who have delivered, maternal age, sex of the neonate and socioeconomic status of the family. Conceptually, the determinants of cord care practice include: place of delivery, location of facilities, and attitude towards cord care.

The location or place of residence will also affect the choice of health service provide as those in urban settlements are likely to get better health services during their Antenatal care and delivery. Rural dwellers have fewer medical facilities that are poorly equipped, most often than not, in terms of medical equipment's and man power and as such lacks the ability to properly care for neonates delivered in such settings (Afolaranmi, et al., 2018). In most rural areas, the restrictions the women face prevented them from accessing healthcare for themselves or their children including healthy umbilical cord care (Rashid et al., 2015). In the rural community, traditional birth attendants make great impact, they are very close to the people and the rural women believe and have trust on them so much that they cannot be easily abolished in the community hence, women always take their advice as to how to care for women and their infants, including the type of material they should use to care for the cord.

In Rivers West, poor neonatal umbilical cord care practice has contributed in no small measure to the neonatal morbidity and mortality among newborns. Though, efforts have been made by governmental and non-governmental organizations in the region to boost maternal and infant healthcare but, it is a known fact that, some women prefer to give birth outside the healthcare facility, and even those who give birth in the facility are discharged to go home and care for their newborns, indicating that, in most cases, the care of the neonatal cord is provided mainly at home except for babies or mothers with complications, who

stay longer in the healthcare facility. Thus, the care of the neonatal cord could be influenced by the socio-cultural and traditional norms around the mother. More worrisome is the fact that, if such norms are inconsistent with recommended practice, the baby stands the risk of contracting infections. This makes it imperative that the expectant mother, especially those in their third trimester be taught the accepted cord care practices before their delivery. Yet, observations have shown that there is either little or no effort made by the healthcare workers to unveil the umbilical cord care practices of these mothers as, family planning, breast feeding and immunization have assumed the central focus for expectant mothers. Though there are insufficient studies on the effects of umbilical infections on the health of the neonate, which cannot be overemphasized. There is therefore the need to investigate the determinants of umbilical cord care practice among mothers. The objectives of the study included to:

1. determine place of delivery (healthcare facility or home) as a determinant to neonatal umbilical cord care practice among mothers attending health centres in Rivers West Senatorial District;
2. determine location of delivery place (rural/urban) as a determinant to neonatal umbilical cord care practice among mothers attending health centres in Rivers West Senatorial District;
3. ascertain attitude toward cord care as a determinant to neonatal umbilical cord care practice among mothers attending health centres in Rivers West Senatorial District;

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant relationship between place of delivery and neonatal umbilical cord care practice among mothers attending health centres in Rivers West Senatorial District.
2. There is no significant relationship between location of delivery place and neonatal umbilical cord care practice among mothers attending health centres in Rivers West Senatorial District.
3. There is no significant relationship between attitude towards cord care and neonatal umbilical cord care practice among mothers attending health centres in Rivers West Senatorial District.

METHODOLOGY

The research design adopted for this study was a descriptive correlational survey design. The study was delimited in geographical coverage to Rivers East Senatorial District. The population for the study consisted of three hundred and fifty-four thousand, five hundred and fifty-six (354,556) postpartum women in Rivers West Senatorial District. The sample size for the study was 880 which was determined using Taro Yemen formula: $N/1+N(e)^2$. A multi-staged sampling procedure was adopted for the study. The procedure involved the following steps: At stage 1, the cluster sampling technique was used to group the senatorial district into two clusters (riverine and upland) based on the terrain and cultural similarities, riverine (AKULGA, ASALGA, Bonny and Degema) and upland (Abua-Odual, Ahoada East, Ahoada West, and Ogba-Egbema-Ndoni LGA). At stage 2, a simple random sampling method was used to select two LGA from each stratum. Stage 3 involves the use of proportionate sampling technique was used to select the number of participants to sample in each Local Government Area (LGA) selected which included: Asari-Toru LGA, Degema, ONELGA and Ahoada West LGA. At stage 4, a simple random sampling method was used to select the participants at each facility.

The study instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire title: Neonatal Umbilical Cord Care Questionnaire (NUCCQ). The questionnaire has four sections A, B, C, and D. Section A focused on the socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents such as location (rural or urban), age, sex, religion and place of birth on a multiple response choice. Section B was focused on the knowledge of umbilical cord care on dichotomous response of Yes or No. Section C elicited responses on the neonatal umbilical cord care practice on a modified Likert scale of Very High Extent, High Extent, Low Extent and Very Low Extent while Section D was designed to gather information on the determinants of umbilical cord care practice on Four Point Likert Scale of strongly agree, agree, disagree and strongly disagree. The validity of the instrument was ascertained by three experts. The reliability co-efficient was established by subjecting the instrument to reliability test using Cronbach alpha. The reliability coefficient found for the whole instrument was 0.763. Thus, the instrument was considered reliable for data collection. Data was collected by a face-to-face delivery of the questionnaire to the respondents. Data was analyzed with the aid of the Statistical Product for Service Solution (SPSS) version 23.0. The retrieved

copies of the questionnaire were coded and analyzed with the aid of SPSS using percentage point biserial correlation at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS

The results of the study are shown below:

Table 1: Point Biserial Correlation showing relationship between place of delivery and cord care practice

Variables		Practice	Place of delivery	Remark
Practice	Pearson correlation	1	0.82	High relationship
	N	811	811	
Place of delivery	Pearson correlation	0.82	1	
	N	811	811	

Guide: 0.00-0.19 = very low, 0.20-0.39 = low, 0.40-0.59 = moderate, 0.60-0.79 = high and ≥ 0.80 is high relationship

Table 1 showed the Point Biserial Correlation between place of delivery and cord care practice. The result revealed a correlation coefficient, $r = 0.82$ indicating a high relationship. Thus, the relationship between place of delivery and cord care practice among mothers attending health centres in Rivers West Senatorial District was high.

Table 2: Point Biserial Correlation showing relationship between location of delivery place and cord care practice

Variables		Practice	Location	Remark
Practice	Pearson correlation	1	0.61	High relationship
	N	811	811	
Location	Pearson correlation	0.61	1	
	N	811	811	

Guide: 0.00-0.19 = very low, 0.20-0.39 = low, 0.40-0.59 = moderate, 0.60-0.79 = high and ≥ 0.80 is high relationship

Table 2 showed the Point Biserial Correlation between location of delivery place and cord care practice. The result revealed a correlation coefficient, $r = 0.61$ indicating a high relationship. Thus, the relationship between location of delivery and cord care practice among mothers attending health centres in Rivers West Senatorial District was high.

Table 3: Point Biserial Correlation showing significant relationship between attitude towards cord care and cord care practice

Variables		Practice	Attitude	Remark
Practice	Pearson correlation	1	0.79	High relationship
	N	811	811	
Attitude	Pearson correlation	0.79	1	
	N	811	811	

Guide: 0.00-0.19 = very low, 0.20-0.39 = low, 0.40-0.59 = moderate, 0.60-0.79 = high and ≥ 0.80 is high relationship

Table 3 showed the Point Biserial Correlation between attitude towards cord care and cord care practice. The result revealed a correlation coefficient, $r = 0.79$ indicating a high relationship. Thus, the relationship

between attitude towards cord care and cord care practice among mothers attending health centres in Rivers West Senatorial District was high.

Table 4: Point Biserial Correlation showing significant relationship between place of delivery and cord care practice

Variables		Practice	Place of delivery	Decision
Practice	Pearson correlation	1	0.82	H ₀ rejected
	N	811	811	
Place of delivery	Pearson correlation	0.82	1	
	N	811	811	

*Significant; $p < 0.05$.

Table 4 presents the Point Biserial Correlation analysis on significant relationship between place of delivery and cord care practice. The result revealed that there was a statistically significant relationship between place of delivery and practice of neonatal umbilical cord care as $p < 0.05$ ($n = 811$; $r = 0.82$; $p = 0.00$). Thus, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant relationship between place of delivery and cord care practice among mothers attending health centres in Rivers West Senatorial District was rejected.

Table 5: Point Biserial Correlation showing significant relationship between location of delivery place and cord care practice

Variables		Practice	Location	Decision
Practice	Pearson correlation	1	0.61	H ₀ rejected
	N	811	811	
Location	Pearson correlation	0.61	1	
	N	811	811	

*Significant; $p < 0.05$.

Table 5 presents the Point Biserial Correlation analysis on significant relationship between location of delivery and cord care practice. The result revealed that there was a statistically significant relationship between location of delivery and practice of neonatal umbilical cord care as $p < 0.05$ ($n = 811$; $r = 0.61$; $p = 0.00$). Thus, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant relationship between location of delivery and cord care practice among mothers attending health centres in Rivers West Senatorial District was rejected.

Table 6: Point Biserial Correlation showing significant relationship between attitude towards cord care and cord care practice

Variables		Practice	Attitude	Decision
Practice	Pearson correlation	1	0.79	H ₀ rejected
	N	811	811	
Attitude	Pearson correlation	0.79	1	
	N	811	811	

*Significant; $p < 0.05$.

Table 6 presents the Point Biserial Correlation analysis on significant relationship between attitude towards cord care and cord care practice. The result revealed that there was a statistically significant relationship between attitude towards cord care and practice of neonatal umbilical cord care as $p < 0.05$ (n

= 811; $r = 0.79$; $p = 0.00$). Thus, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant relationship between attitude towards cord care and cord care practice among mothers attending health centres in Rivers West Senatorial District was rejected.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings of the study are discussed below:

The result revealed that there was a statistically significant relationship between place of delivery and practice of neonatal umbilical cord care as ($n = 811$; $r = 0.82$; $p < 0.05$). This shows that place of delivery has the highest extent of determining cord care practice. The finding of this study is in line with that of Patricia and Siobhan (2017) whose study conducted in Uttar Pradesh (India) showed that facility based child birth was greatly associated with appropriate new born care practices. Facility based child birth had a strong association with appropriate new born care probably because of the ease with which medical advice on appropriate new born practices can be obtained and given.

The result revealed that there was a statistically significant relationship between location of delivery and practice of neonatal umbilical cord care as ($n = 811$; $r = 0.61$; $p < 0.05$). The location or place of residence will also affect the choice of health service provide as those in urban settlements are likely to get better health services during their Antenatal care and delivery. Rural dwellers have fewer medical facilities that are poorly equipped, most often than not, in terms of medical equipment's and man power and as such lacks the ability to properly care for neonates delivered in such settings (Afolaranmi, et al., 2018). In most rural areas, the restrictions the women face prevented them from accessing healthcare for themselves or their children including healthy umbilical cord care (Rashid et al., 2015). In the rural community, traditional birth attendants make great impact, they are very close to the people and the rural women believe and have trust on them so much that they cannot be easily abolished in the community hence, women always take their advice as to how to care for women and their infants, including the type of material they should use to care for the cord. The homogeneity of the study population could be implicated for the similarity found between the present study and the previous one.

The result revealed that there was a statistically significant relationship between attitude towards cord care and practice of neonatal umbilical cord care as ($n = 811$; $r = 0.79$; $p < 0.05$). This finding is also expected because attitude which is a predisposition towards any health behaviour is a strong force behind any health practice including hygienic umbilical cord care practice. The finding of this study is in consonance with that of Chizoma et al. (2020) whose study on the umbilical cord care practices of mothers attending selected Primary Health Care Centres in Ibadan, Nigeria showed that attitude towards cord care is related to its practice among women. The homogeneity of the study population could explain for the similarity found between the present study and previous ones they were both carried out among mothers who has father. The finding of this study gives credence to Roro et al. (2015) which showed a relationship between attitude and practice. The homogeneity of the study population could be implicated for the similarity found between the present study and the previous one.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that had good knowledge of neonatal umbilical cord care and the determinants of umbilical cord care practice among mothers attending health centres in Rivers West Senatorial District were: place of delivery, location of delivery, and attitude towards cord care.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Government should make delivery in Primary healthcare facilities free of charge to encourage women deliver in healthcare facilities where they can be monitored and assisted in the proper care of the neonatal umbilical cord.
2. Governmental and Non-governmental organizations should extend help to women in the rural areas as well as urban areas and provide them with necessary resources and information needed

for hygienic cord care practices or subsidize all products that are needed for proper cord care practice in all health care facilities where antenatal and postnatal services are rendered.

3. Colleges of health Science, schools of nursing and midwifery, should make it mandatory for health students in training to go for community mobilization to create awareness among women in rural communities on ideal cord care practices.

REFERENCES

- Abhulimhen-Iyoha, B.I., & Ibadin, M.O. (2015). Determinants of cord care practices among mothers in Benin City, Edo state, Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal Clinical Practice*, 15, 210–223. <http://doi.org/10.4103/1119-3077.97320>.
- Abhulimhen-Iyoha, B.I., Ofili A., & Ibadin, M.O. (2015). Cord care practices among mothers attending immunization clinic at the University of Benin Teaching Hospital, Benin City. *Nigeria Journal Paediatrics*, 38(3), 104–108.
- Afolaranmi, O.T. (2015). Knowledge and practice of food safety and hygiene among food vendors in primary school in Jos, Plateau State, North Central Nigeria. *Journal of Medical Research*, <http://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2018.00010>.
- Afolaranmi, T. O., Hassan, Z. I., Akinyemi, O. O., Sule, S. S., Maleté, M. U., Choji, C. P., & Bello, D. A. (2018). Cord care practices: A perspective of contemporary african setting. *Frontiers of Public Health*, <http://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2018.00010>.
- Asiedu, S.S.O., Apatu, N.A.A., Tetteh, R., & Hodgson, A. (2019). Neonatal Cord Care Practices among Mothers and Caregivers in the Volta Region of Ghana. *International Journal of Maternal and Child Health and Aids*, 8(1), 63 - 69.
- Chizoma, M.N., Fisayo, O.M., & Abimbola, O.O. (2020). Umbilical cord care knowledge and practices of mothers attending selected Primary Health Care Centres in Ibadan, Nigeria. *International Journal of Caring Science*, 13(1), 143–151.
- Dhingra, U., Gittelsohn, J., & Suleiman, A. M. (2015). Delivery, immediate newborn and cord care practices in Pemba Tanzania: A qualitative study of community, hospital staff and community level care providers for knowledge, attitudes, belief systems and practices. *BioMedical Central Pregnancy Childbirth*, 14(1), 173-179.
- Ibrahim, S., Mikayir, G., Yekta, C., Salih, G., Isik, R., Konukoglu, R., et al. (2015) Skin burn in two term newborn due to use of 70% alcohol for umbilical care: Case report. *The Journal of Kartal Training and Research Hospital*, 22, 75-78. <https://doi.org/10.5505/jkartaltr.2015.42275>
- Lawn, J. E., Blencowe, H., & Oza, S. (2015). Every newborn: Progress, priorities, and potential beyond survival. *Lancet*, 384(9938), 189–205.
- Linhares, E. F., Martins, L. A., & Dias, J. A. (2015). Educating to care for the newborn: Prevention of omphalitis and neonatal tetanus—experience report. *Revista de Enfermagem*, 8, 2539-2544
- Ministry of Health (2018). *Chlorhexidine Digluconate 7.1% Gel: The newly recommended product for newborn umbilical cord care in Ghana*. Ministry of Health.
- Muriuki, A., Obare, F., Ayieko, B., Matanda, D., Sisimwo, K., & Mdawida, B. (2017). Health care providers' perspectives regarding the use of chlorhexidine gel for cord care in neonates in rural Kenya: Implications for scale-up. *Biomedical Central Health Service Research*, 17(1), 305-313.
- Nosan, G., & Para-Panjan, D. (2017). Umbilical cord care: national survey, literature review and recommendations. *Journal of Maternal-Fetal and Neonatal Medicine*, <https://doi.org/10.1080/14767058.2016.1220530>
- Okpaleke, M. H. (2017). Using 7.1% chlorhexidine gel for umbilical cord care: Implication for WHO's recommendation for a standard cord care practice. *Asian Journal of Research of Medicine and Pharmacy Science*, 1(2), 1–6.
- Osuchukwu, E. C., Ezeruigbo, C. S. F. & Eko, J. E. (2017). Knowledge of standard umbilical cord management among mothers in Calabar South Local Government Area, Cross River State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Nursing Science*, 7(3), 57–62.

- Padiyath, A., Bhat, A. V., & Ekambaram, B. M. (2015). Knowledge, attitude and practice of neonatal care among postnatal mothers. *Current Pediatric Research*, 14(2), 147-152.
- Roro MA, Hassen EM, Lemma A.M. & Gebreyesus, S.H. (2015). Why do women not deliver in health facilities: a qualitative study of the community perspectives in south central Ethiopia? *BioMedical Central Research Notes*, 7(1), 1-7.
- Sacks, E., Moss, W. J., Winch, P. J., Thuma, P., Dijk, J. H., & Van Mullany, L. C. (2015). Skin, thermal and umbilical cord care practices for neonates in southern rural Zambia: A qualitative study. *BioMedical Central Pregnancy Childbirth*, 15, 1-11.
- Walsh, S. M., Norr, K. F., Sipsma, H., Cordes, L. A., & Sankar, G. (2017). Effectiveness of a campaign to implement chlorhexidine use for newborns in rural Haiti. *BioMedical Central Research Notes*, 10(1), 742-749.
- World Health Organization (2016). *New-borns: reducing mortality Fact sheet*. WHO.
- World Health Organization (2017). *Neonatal mortality*. WHO.